

A theoretical approach to Fano resonances in plasmonic dolmens: Determination of Fano resonance energies for single and multiple modes

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Abstract. We show that Fano resonance spectrum in plasmonic dolmens can be found from the oriented coupled dipoles model. It is also shown that multiple Fano resonance spectrum can also be derived if the two excitation modes of the nanorods are taken into account

Figure 1. A dolmen structure of plasmonic nanorods.

Let L , W and T be the length, width and the thickness of each nanorod. We first study the single mode case by assuming a very high aspect ratio so that the nanorods polarize only along their long axes and we assign the same Lorentzian polarizability α_L to all three identical nanorods.

Since we assume a very high aspect ratio we focus only on the x component of the induced dipole of the horizontal rod. By applying the oriented dipoles method given in [1] we calculate the x component of the scattered far field due to the horizontal rod [2]:

$$P_{1x} = \mu_L(1 + \alpha_L\delta_1)E_x \quad (1)$$

where $\mu_L = \varepsilon\alpha_L/(1 + \alpha_L\delta_1 - 2\alpha_L^2\delta_2^2)$, $\delta_1 = k^2A(D)$, $\delta_2 = k^2hDB(d)/2d^2$, E_x is the x component of the applied electric field and the coupling coefficients $A(D)$ and $B(d)$ are defined as follows:

$$A(D) = \left(1 + \frac{i}{kD} - \frac{1}{k^2D^2}\right)g(D), \quad (2)$$

$$B(d) = \left(-1 - \frac{3i}{kd} + \frac{3}{k^2d^2} \right) g(d), \quad (3)$$

$$g(r) = e^{ikr}/4\pi r.$$

Fano dip occurs at energy that satisfies $1 + \alpha_L \delta_1 = 0$. Particularly, this happens at $Im(\alpha_L \delta_1) = 0$. It is also possible to calculate the energies that correspond to the resonance peaks from the denominator of μ_L . Peaks occur at energies that satisfy $Re(\mu_L) = 0$

If we work with wider nanorods we have to take into account the effect of the transverse polarizability α_W [3]. In this rather complicated case, in order to simplify the calculations we assume that the contribution of the vertical nanorods to the x component of the scattered far field is still much less than that of the horizontal nanorod. When we consider both longitudinal and transverse modes P_{1x} reads as follows:

$$P_{1x} = \mu_{W,L}(1 + \alpha_L \delta_1)(1 + \alpha_W \delta_2)E_x \quad (4)$$

Where $\delta_1 = k^2 A(D)$, if we let $D = d$ for simplicity $\delta_2 = k^2(A(D) - B(D)/2)$.

In this case, according to Eq.(4) we have two Fano dips and they occur at energies that satisfy $Im(\alpha_L \delta_1) = 0$ and $Im(\alpha_W \delta_2) = 0$. $\mu_{W,L}$ is the overall coefficient for the double mode that determines the resonance peaks at energies that satisfy $Re(\mu_{W,L}) = 0$, but now $\mu_{W,L}$ does have a simple form even for $D = d$.

- [1] Kuntman MA, Kuntman E, Sancho-Parramon J and Arteaga O 2018 *Physical Review B* **98** 045410
- [2] For the single mode case $\mathbf{J}_1 = \alpha_L \mathbf{J}_H$ is the polarization matrix associated with the horizontal nanorod and $\mathbf{J}_2 = \mathbf{J}_3 = \alpha_L \mathbf{J}_V$ is the polarization matrix associated with the vertical nanorods, where \mathbf{J}_H and \mathbf{J}_V are the usual Jones matrices corresponding to horizontal and vertical linear polarizers.
- [3] For the double mode, $\mathbf{J}_1 = \alpha_L \mathbf{J}_H + \alpha_W \mathbf{J}_V$ is the polarization matrix associated with the horizontal nanorod and $\mathbf{J}_2 = \mathbf{J}_3 = \alpha_W \mathbf{J}_H + \alpha_L \mathbf{J}_V$ is the polarization matrix associated with the vertical nanorods.